

For The Attention of The Clerk to the Committee on Constitutional, Legal and Parliamentary Affairs:

Memorandum relating to the Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021

30th September 2021

Title: Opposition to the Bill on grounds of concern for psychological (and other) harm to citizens of Ghana

As a mental health professional I consider it my duty, as a citizen of Ghana, to speak to the professional, ethical and humanitarian concerns I have for the impact of this proposed bill on the wellbeing and health of fellow citizens of Ghana. Inevitably there will therefore, also be a knock on effect to the economy of our country. I consider my perspective to be in keeping with the values and statements of our own constitution.

Health and Wellbeing Concerns About the Proposed Bill:

The bill seeks to further criminalise and condemn individuals with minority identity status - either through their sexuality, intersex status or gender non-conformity. It seeks to coerce or require that they engage in conversion therapy or have surgery if they are intersex. This is stated as being for their benefit and to the benefit of our country. The mutually consensual activities and the existence of those bearing these identities however, cause no psychological or physical harm to others. On the other hand, research evidence for the harm from conversion therapy has led to the UN now calling for it to be banned internationally. Though many may feel forced to seek conversion therapy or surgery due to increasing hostility (which is in fact being whipped up by this bill and the dialogue around it) the UN 2020 report recognises the 'severe pain and suffering' that can often result 'in long-lasting psychological and physical damage' despite people initially attempting to comply (<https://www.ohchr.org/en/NewsEvents/Pages/DisplayNews.aspx?NewsID=26051&LangID=E>). Mandatory or coercive surgery on intersex individuals has also been found to cause severe harm as survivors report and as detailed in a United Nations OHCHR report, 2020 (<https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/26410397.2020.1731298>). This bill will contribute to increasing levels of trauma for many individuals which is why I must speak out as a medical professional whose ethical duty is 'to do no harm'.

Because these approaches will be recommended or mandated, many will not feel safe to reach out for therapeutic, medical or even social or religious support despite the needs they may have. This may contribute to the development of severe mental health

